

AI-based Robust Linear Quadratic Regulator Controller for Quadcopter System

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Abstract

Accurate performance control of a quadcopter system necessitates rapid response and effective tracking of control variables such as speed, position, and torque. While traditional methods, such as the PID control approach, ensure stability in closed-loop control, they often fail to account for the nonlinear conditions present in the environment. Uncertainties can arise from unmodeled dynamics and nonlinear effects that are overlooked during the linearization of the system equations, as well as from disturbances and noise. In this paper, we employ a robust proportional-derivative(double)+LQR method as the primary control strategy. Our study focuses on four state variables—altitude, roll angle, pitch angle, and yaw angle—to manage quadcopter movements. To optimize the PDD parameters, we utilize the DEA algorithm. This approach demonstrates effective real-time tracking of parameters while accommodating disturbances.

Key Words: *Quadcopter System, Linear Quadratic Regulator, Proportional-Derivative(Double), Differential Evolution Algorithm*

Table 1: Nomenclature

$c\theta$: $\cos\theta$
$s\theta$: $\sin\theta$
m	: mass of the quadcopter
g	: acceleration of gravity
K	: Propeller specific constant in normal direction
k_m	: Propeller specific constant in reverse direction
ω	: Angular speed
F	: Aerodynamic force
J	: Symmetric positive definite inertia matrix
J_r	: rotor's inertia
M_B	: Total torque
F_b	: Aerodynamic thrust forces
k_1	: Controller parameter
Ω_p	: Parallel component of Ω to the vector of q_v
Ω_n	: Normal component of Ω to the vector of q_v
k_T	: Total gain of the LQR+PD2 controller
k_e	: System's error gain
E	: Error signal
Q	: Weighting matrix (Positive semi-definite symmetric matrix)
R	: Weighting matrix (Positive definite symmetric matrix)
$x_j^{g,i}$: Variable j of individual i in generation g
CR	: Crossover rate
c	: Learning factor
S_{CR}	: Set of indices

1- Introduction

A quadrotor, commonly known as a quadcopter, is a type of vertical flight drone that utilizes four propellers arranged in a cross configuration. This design enables the drone to move smoothly and uniformly in all directions, offering excellent maneuverability. Quadcopters are available in a variety of sizes, ranging from just a few centimeters to several meters [1]. In this design, the angle of the propellers remains constant, and the lifting force is adjusted solely by varying the rotation speed of the rotors. Additionally, the direction of rotation for all four rotors is fixed and oriented perpendicular to the main frame. In order to neutralize the frictional torque, the rotation direction of the front and rear rotors is opposite to that of the left and right rotors. Quadcopters are now widely used in the fields of telecommunications, global navigation, and meteorological research. Among the civilian uses of quadcopters, it can also mention the Fukushima accident in Japan, where quadcopters were used to investigate the damage caused to this power plant. Quadcopters also play an important and effective role in identifying and tracking ships that illegally catch marine creatures such as fish or extinguishing fires and where flying is dangerous for the pilot [2].

Nowadays, the mini-drones are used in several applications such as monitoring of the airspace and urban traffic, natural risk management (e.g. volcano activities), measurement of air pollution, agriculture industry and film production [3]. Since Quad-rotor Flying robots use four rotors instead of one rotor to provide thrust to the robot, it has four input forces and six output coordinates. This enables the quad-rotor flying robot to carry heavier weights [4]. Most of the quad-rotor flying robots change its direction by manipulation of the individual rotor's speed and does not require cyclic and collective pitch control. The mechanical design is hence simpler and consequently reduces the production cost of the flying robot [5]. However, there are a few shortcomings to consider. The space requirement for the four rotors and the associated power consumption are the primary drawbacks of this design. Four rotors with cross frame configuration are definitely consuming more space compare to the conventional UAVs which have only one rotor [6]. Although minimal cross-coupling simplifies the dynamics of the quadrotor, the inherent dynamics, particularly its low rate damping, can make the vehicle challenging to control. The

challenge of controlling the vehicle can be even more difficult for a small, low cost flying vehicle [7]. In general, existing quadrotor dynamic models are developed on the hypothesis of a unique rigid body which is a restrictive hypothesis that does not account for the fact that the system is composed of five rigid bodies: Four rotors and a crossing body frame. Some literature has presented attitude control schemes, such as feedback control for large-angle rotational maneuvers [8], switching model predictive control [9], robust margin for attitude control [10], bounded control based on the quaternion [11], sliding mode control based on the extended observer [12], disturbance rejection tracking control based on quaternion [13], and robust attitude control [14]. However, trajectory tracking control for this type of system is more challenging because achieving global stability analysis is difficult due to the coupling properties involved. In the proposed approach, the DEA algorithm is employed to regulate the parameters of the LQR system, ensuring a robust control strategy. This paper provides an innovative approach to control the quadcopter dynamics to improve its performance. In this regard, the modified LQR control strategy is used. Among the main contributions of the proposed approach, the following can be mentioned:

- Designing an innovative modified LQR system for controlling the operation of quadcopter
- Using DEA algorithm for improving the level of robustness under presence of different kind of disturbances

Methodology

The linear quadratic regulator (LQR) control is an advance control technique which provides a systematic approach for automatic adjustment of controllers in real time, in order to achieve or to maintain a desired level of control system performance, when the parameters of the plant dynamic model are unknown and/or change by the time [9]. An optimal control strategy for yaw control of a quadcopter has been developed using a linear quadratic regulator (LQR). The quadcopter's dynamics are modeled to describe its behavior in three-dimensional space. The LQR-based controller is specifically designed to manage the quadcopter's orientation in the yaw direction. This approach is justified by the model's low moment of inertia and six degrees of freedom, which contribute to the quadcopter's enhanced stability. The performance of this control framework is evaluated through simulations on a mathematical model of the quadcopter, under both normal and perturbed conditions, using the MATLAB platform. The linear quadratic regulator (LQR) control is an advance control technique which provides a systematic. The schematic representation of the quadrotor is shown in Fig. (1). Quadcopter is a 6 DOF aircraft, so there are 6 variables (x , y , z , ϕ , θ and φ) that are used to express its orientation in space. ϕ , θ , and φ are also known as Euler's angles. According to Fig. (1), four arms of the quadcopter are symmetric and at the end of each arm one motor is mounted to rotate the propeller. F_1 , F_2 , F_3 and F_4 are the upward thrust forces generated by the angular speeds ω_1 , ω_2 , ω_3 , and ω_4 of motors, respectively. Roll, pitch and yaw angles about the x , y and z axes are denoted by Φ , θ , and ψ , respectively. The arm length of the quadcopter frame is denoted by l . Details of each variable are as follows:

- x & y : These variables are used to represent the position of quadrotor in space.
- z : Defines the altitude of quadrotor
- ϕ : ϕ or Roll angle it represent angle about the x -axis
- θ : θ or Pitch angle it represent angle about the y -axis
- φ : φ or Yaw angle it represent angle about the z -axis

Fig. 1: Schematic representation of the quadrotor [1]

Kinematic Model

As shown in Fig. 1., the body fixed frame is represented by x - y - z , while the inertial frame is represented by X - Y - Z . The transformation between these two frames is represented by the transformation matrix R (Eq. (1)), which is obtained by the Euler angles (Φ , θ , and ψ) about x , y and z axes.

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} c\theta c\psi & s\Phi s\theta c\psi - c\Phi s\psi & c\Phi s\theta c\psi + s\Phi s\psi \\ c\theta s\psi & s\Phi s\theta s\psi - c\Phi c\psi & c\Phi s\theta s\psi - s\Phi c\psi \\ -s\theta & s\Phi c\theta & c\Phi c\theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Dynamic Model

The movement status of the quadcopter can be presented by the Euler torque equation. According to Fig. (1), ω_1 and ω_3 are rotate in clockwise direction, while ω_2 and ω_4 rotate in anticlockwise direction to balance the torque about the z axis. Each propeller applies a normal force (F_i) (Eq. (2)) and an aerodynamic moment (M_i) (Eq. (3)) in the normal direction. The torque applied to each propeller on the vehicle body can be obtained by Eq. (4) [15].

$$F_i = K_i \omega_i^2 \quad i = 1, \dots, 4 \quad (2)$$

$$M_i = k_m \omega_i^2 \quad i = 1, \dots, 4 \quad (3)$$

$$M_{pi} = \pm \left(M_i \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} + \Omega J_r \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \omega_i \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (4)$$

Rotational equations

The rotational movements can be explained by Eq. (5) with using Euler torque equation. The total torque applied to the system can be explained by Eq.(7).

$$J\dot{\Omega} + \Omega \times J\Omega + J_r\Omega \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \omega_r \end{bmatrix} = M_B \quad (5)$$

$$\omega_r = \omega_1 - \omega_2 + \omega_3 - \omega_4 \quad (6)$$

$$M_B = [M_x \quad M_y \quad M_z]^T \quad (7)$$

$$M_x = F_2 l - F_4 l = lK(\omega_2^2 - \omega_4^2)$$

$$M_y = F_3 l - F_1 l = lK(\omega_3^2 - \omega_1^2)$$

$$M_z = M_1 - M_2 + M_3 - M_4$$

Translational equations

The translation equations based on Newton's second law for the quadcopter can be described by Eq. (8) to Eq. (13). The aerodynamic thrust forces and the inputs of the propeller system are explained by Eq. (14) and Eq. (15), respectively.

$$m\ddot{X} = (F_1 + F_2 + F_3 + F_4)(c\Phi s\theta c\psi + s\Phi s\psi) \quad (8)$$

$$m\ddot{Y} = (F_1 + F_2 + F_3 + F_4)(c\Phi s\theta c\psi + s\Phi s\psi) \quad (9)$$

$$m\ddot{Z} = (F_1 + F_2 + F_3 + F_4)(c\Phi c\theta) - mg \quad (10)$$

$$I_x\ddot{\Phi} = (F_1 - F_3)l + \dot{\theta}\dot{\psi}(I_y - I_z) \quad (11)$$

$$I_y\ddot{\theta} = (F_2 - F_4)l + \dot{\Phi}\dot{\psi}(I_z - I_x) \quad (12)$$

$$I_z\ddot{\psi} = (M_2 + M_4 - M_1 - M_3)l + \dot{\theta}\dot{\Phi}(I_x - I_y) \quad (13)$$

$$F_b = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ k_f(\omega_1^2 + \omega_2^2 + \omega_3^2 + \omega_4^2) \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

$$U = [u_1 \quad u_2 \quad u_3 \quad u_4]^T = [M_x \quad M_y \quad M_z \quad F_b]^T \quad (15)$$

Differential Evolution Algorithm

The Differential Evolution (DE) algorithm is a global computer search algorithm introduced in 1995 by an American research team and was initially introduced to solve Chebyshev polynomials [16]. In the evolution phase, two individuals are selected from the population of the previous generation, and through the crossover operation, two children are selected for the next generation. There is a variety of crossover operators, however the Eq. (16) is used in this project for this purpose. Based on the gaussian distribution function (Eq. (17)), the output is in the range of [0.0,1.0].

$$u_j^{g+1,i} = \begin{cases} x_j^{g,i} & \text{if } r \leq CR^i \\ x_j^{g,r_1} & \text{if } r_0 \leq 0.5 \\ x_j^{g,r_2} & \text{o. w.} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

$$\mu_{CR} = (1.0 - c) \times \mu_{CR} + c \times \frac{\sum_{i \in S_{CR}} CR^i}{|S_{CR}|} \quad (17)$$

After generating a chain of variables both for the current and the next generation, the mutation operator is used to increase the search probability of finding points outside the local range. To perform the mutation operation, polynomial mutation is used in this project [22]. In the evolving stage, Eq. (18) is used for each generation. The meaning of r is a uniform random number generated in the interval [0.0,1.0]. Eq. (19) is used to create mutations on the created children. The flowchart of this method is shown in Fig. (2).

$$u_j^{g+1,i} = \begin{cases} x_j^{g,r_5} & \text{if } r \leq CR_B^i \\ x_j^{g,i} & \text{o. w.} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

$$x_j^{g+1,i} = \begin{cases} 1 - u_j^{g+1,i} & \text{if } r \leq pm \\ u_j^{g+1,i} & \text{o. w.} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

Control Design Method

In this project PDD+LQR method is used as a main controller. The LQR approach is a feedback controller which the output is obtained by controller’s gain K. [17]. In this study, four state variables consist of altitude, roll angle, pitch angle and yaw angle are considered to control quadcopter movements. So, defined variables are presented in Equ. (20). The error signal (E) is equal to difference between real output (y) and desired input (r_d) (Eq. (21)). According to proposed control strategy, the control signal for the quadcopter system can be considered as Eq. (22). In this relation, K is total gain of the LQR+PDD controller. Finally, the control input signal of the system is obtained as Eq. (23)

$$x = [Z, \dot{Z}, \varphi, \dot{\varphi}, \theta, \dot{\theta}, \psi, \dot{\psi}]^T \tag{20}$$

$$E = -y + r_d \tag{21}$$

$$u = -K + E \tag{22}$$

$$K = k_p y + (k_{d1} + k_{d2}) \frac{dy}{dt} \tag{23}$$

For regulating the PDD parameters, the DEA algorithm is used. For achieving the optimum output, the cost function is designed as Equ. (24) [20]. Q and R are the weighting matrices that are used for control the state variables. The block diagram of the proposed method is shown in Fig. (3).

$$J = \int_0^{\infty} (x^T Q x + u^T R u) dt \tag{24}$$

$$A^T P + P A + Q - P B R^{-1} \cdot B^T P = 0 \tag{25}$$

Fig. 2: Flowchart of differential evaluation method [19]**Stability analysis**

Suppose that the process model represented by state space as Eq. (26). A_p and B_p are matrix and vector of unknown constant parameters. u is the output signal of the controller and x is the state vector. If the reference model is defined as Eq. (27), then the control law can be selected as Eq. (29). Then the control law is selected as Eq. (36). In this relation, L_r and L_x are matrices that containing the parameters of the controller. Also, u_c is the reference signal.

$$\dot{x} = A_p x + B_p u \quad (26)$$

$$y = Cx \quad (27)$$

$$\dot{x}_m = A_m x_m + B_m u_c \quad (28)$$

$$y = C_m x_m \quad (29)$$

$$u = L_r u_c - L_x \quad (30)$$

The closed loop system is expressed as Eq. (31). Now, the error equation can be presented as Eq. (32). Differentiating the error with respect to time can be presented by Eq. (33). So, the Eq. (34) can be derived. The error goes to zero if A_m is stable and $A - A_m = 0$ & $B - B_m = 0$. We can define the following Lyapunov function for parameter adaptation law (Eq. (35)). In this regard, P is positive definite matrix and V is positive definite function. If its first derivative to time V is not positive definite, then V is a Lyapunov function. Now the derivative of V regard to time can be solved as Eq. (36). In this regard, Q is a positive definite matrix such that meet the following relation (Eq. (37)). Therefore, if we choose a stable A_m matrix, we will get always P and Q positive definite matrix. Accordingly, the derivative of time of function V is calculated as Eq. (38). It should be noted that the function V is a Lyapunov function negative semi-definite ensures the output error between the real system and the reference model will tend to be zero and the system is asymptotically stable.

$$\dot{x} = (A_p - B_p L) x + B_p L_r u_c = A(\theta) x + B(\theta) u_c \quad (31)$$

$$e = x - x_m \quad (32)$$

$$\frac{de}{dt} = \frac{dx}{dt} - \frac{dx_m}{dt} = A_p x + B_p u - A_m x_m - B_m u_c \quad (33)$$

$$\frac{de}{dt} = A_m e + (A(\theta) - A_m) x + (B(\theta) - B_m) u_c \quad (34)$$

$$V = e^T P e + \text{tr}(A(\theta) - A_m)^T Q_a (A(\theta) - A_m) + \text{tr}(B(\theta) - B_m)^T Q_b (B(\theta) - B_m) \quad (35)$$

$$\frac{dV}{dt} = e^T P A_m e + e^T A_m^T P e + 2 \text{tr}(A(\theta) - A_m)^T (Q_a \dot{A} + P e x^T) \quad (36)$$

$$+ 2 \text{tr}(B(\theta) - B_m)^T (Q_b \dot{B} + P e u_c^T)$$

$$A_m^T P + P A_m = -Q \quad (37)$$

$$\frac{dV}{dt} = -e^T Q e \quad (38)$$

Fig. 3: Block diagram of the proposed control approach

Results evaluation

Characteristics of quadcopter and controller

In this section, the parameters of quadcopter and controller's parameters are listed in Table (1) and Table (2), respectively. In order to evaluate the proposed control approach, it is assumed that the regulator has variable operating conditions. The amount of speed deviation error from the desired value is presented in Fig. (4). The amount of difference between the angles φ , θ , ψ with the determined reference values are also shown by Fig. (5) to (7). The amount of error along the axes of x, y and z are also shown in Fig. (8) to (10) respectively.

Table 1: Quadcopter main parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Mass	m	1.2	kg
Thrust coefficient	k_t	$3.13 \cdot 10^{-5}$	Ns^2
Length	l	0.2	M
Drag coefficient	K_d	$7.5 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$Nm.s^2$
Moment inertia for x-axis	I_x	$2.353 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$kg.m^2$
Moment inertia for y-axis	I_y	$2.400 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$kg.m^2$
Moment inertia for z-axis	I_z	$2.262 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$kg.m^2$

Table 2: Parameters of LQR controller

Movement	Gain K	Q matrix	R matrix
Pitch	[0.0192 0.1162 0.0001]	$\begin{bmatrix} 3 \cdot 8 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 32 \cdot 14 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \cdot 922 \end{bmatrix}$	[1]
Roll	[0.0180 0.0675 0.0002]	$\begin{bmatrix} 3 \cdot 8 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 32 \cdot 14 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \cdot 922 \end{bmatrix}$	[1]
Yaw	[0.0183 5.6692]	$\begin{bmatrix} 3 \cdot 8 & 0 \\ 0 & 32 \cdot 14 \end{bmatrix}$	[1]
Z - axis	[1.3355 5.6692]	$\begin{bmatrix} 3 \cdot 8 & 0 \\ 0 & 32 \cdot 14 \end{bmatrix}$	[1]

Fig. 4: Speed deviation error from desired output

Fig. 5: Comparison of desired vs. real values of φ

Fig. 6: Comparison of desired vs. real values of θ

Fig. 7: Comparison of desired vs. real values of ψ

Fig. 8: Comparison of speed error in x axis

Fig. 9: Comparison of speed error in y axis

Fig. 10: Comparison of speed error in z axis

Tracking performance of the controller

In Fig. (11) the angular speed values of the quadcopter are shown for two status: reference (desired values) and real (measured values). As can be seen, the angular speed at the time of changes in the reference speed has been able to track the desired value and reach convergence at the proper time. The error value of the rotation angle is also shown in Fig. (12).

Fig. 11: Comparison between desired vs. real frequency of rotor

Fig. 12: The error value for position of rotor's angle

Applying disturbance to the input signal

A test signal has been used to evaluate the performance of the proposed approach. This signal has a disturbance as stated in Equ. (45). This test signal contains 5 harmonics, a Gaussian noise with mean and variance values equal to zero and one, respectively. K_s coefficient is considered equal to 0.05. Since there is always a mechanical deviation for any mechanical system, therefore the introduced control method has been tested against these deviations. For this purpose, mechanical deviation $\Delta F = -1$ HZ has been used. This deviation is applied at the beginning of the second cycle and is fixed after 33ms. Because the harmonics are positive multiples of the fundamental frequency, the deviation in the fundamental frequency affects all the harmonics. The results of estimating the amplitude and phase of the fundamental harmonic are presented in Fig. (13) and (14).

$$\begin{aligned}
 y(t) = & 1.5 \sin(\omega t + 80^\circ) + .1/2 \sin(3\omega t + 60^\circ) \\
 & + 1/5 \sin(5\omega t + 45^\circ) + 1/8 \sin(7\omega t + 36^\circ) \\
 & + 1/10 \sin(11\omega t + 30^\circ) + K_s \text{rand}(t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{45}$$

Fig. 13: Tracking of the fundamental harmonic

Fig. 14: Tracking of the phase of fundamental harmonic

Conclusion

Accurate control of a quadcopter system requires rapid response and effective tracking of control variables such as speed, position, and torque. The quality of the mechanical torque produced by an electric linear regulator is dependent on the precision of measurement and control of state variables, including voltage and current. In this project, the PDD+LQR method is employed as the primary control strategy. The LQR approach is a feedback controller which the output is obtained by controller's gain K . In this study, four state variables consist of altitude, roll angle, pitch angle and yaw angle are considered to control quadcopter movements. For regulating the PDD parameters, the DEA algorithm is used. For achieving the optimum output, the cost function is designed and Q and R matrices are the weighting matrices that are used for control the state variables. For determining the optimal value for K , the Riccati equation is used. As can be seen from the simulation results, this algorithm shows good performance in real-time tracking of parameters.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ata, Baris, and Mashar Cenk Gencal. "Comparison of optimization approaches on linear quadratic regulator design for trajectory tracking of a quadrotor." *Evolutionary Intelligence*(2024): 1-16.
- [2] Shahbazi, H., and V. Tikani. "Design of a nonlinear controller on quadrotor drone using combined method of gradient particle swarm optimization." *system* 1, no. 1 (2018).
- [3] Albedran, Hazim, and Károly Jármai. "Evolutionary control system of asymmetric quadcopter." *International Review of Applied Sciences and Engineering* 14, no. 3 (2023): 374-382.
- [4] Bai, Songnan, Qiqi Pan, Runze Ding, Huaiyuan Jia, Zhengbao Yang, and Pakpong Chirarattananon. "An agile monopedal hopping quadcopter with synergistic hybrid locomotion." *Science Robotics* 9, no. 89 (2024): eadi8912.
- [5] Takva, Çağatay, and Zeynep Yeşim İlerisoy. "Flying Robot Technology (Drone) Trends: A Review in the Building and Construction Industry." *Architecture, Civil Engineering, Environment* 16, no. 1 (2023): 47-68.
- [6] Muhamad, Aidil, Seno Darmawan Panjaitan, and Redi Ratiandi Yacoub. "Design and development of flight controller for quadcopter drone control." *Telecommunications, Computers, and Electricals Engineering Journal (TELECTRICAL)* 1, no. 3 (2024): 279-291.
- [7] Lee, Ji-Won, Nguyen Xuan-Mung, Ngoc Phi Nguyen, and Sung Kyung Hong. "Adaptive altitude flight control of quadcopter under ground effect and time-varying load: Theory and experiments." *Journal of Vibration and Control* 29, no. 3-4 (2023): 571-581.
- [8] Stone, H. "Aerodynamic modeling and simulation of a wing-in-slipstream tailsitter UAV." In *Biennial AIAA International Powered Lift Conference, Williamsburg, Virginia*, pp. 2-4. 2002.
- [9] Lee, Taeyoung. "Exponential stability of an attitude tracking control system on SO (3) for large-angle rotational maneuvers." *Systems & Control Letters* 61, no. 1 (2012): 231-237.
- [10] Alexis, Kostas, George Nikolakopoulos, and Anthony Tzes. "Switching model predictive attitude control for a quadrotor helicopter subject to atmospheric disturbances." *Control Engineering Practice* 19, no. 10 (2011): 1195-1207.
- [11] Lara, David, Gerardo Romero, Anand Sanchez, Rogelio Lozano, and Alfredo Guerrero. "Robustness margin for attitude control of a four rotor mini-rotorcraft: Case of study." *Mechatronics* 20, no. 1 (2010): 143-152.
- [12] Guerrero-Castellanos, J. Fermi, Nicolas Marchand, Ahmad Hably, Suzanne Lesecq, and Jérôme Delamare. "Bounded attitude control of rigid bodies: Real-time experimentation to a quadrotor mini-helicopter." *Control Engineering Practice* 19, no. 8 (2011): 790-797.
- [13] Zhang, Ruifeng, Quan Quan, and K-Y. Cai. "Attitude control of a quadrotor aircraft subject to a class of time-varying disturbances." *IET control theory & applications* 5, no. 9 (2011): 1140-1146.
- [14] Zhang, Xuxi, and Daizhan Cheng. "Nonlinear internal model based attitude tracking and disturbance rejection." *Asian Journal of Control* 14, no. 5 (2012): 1397-1402.
- [15] Nagaty, Amr, Sajad Saeedi, Carl Thibault, Mae Seto, and Howard Li. "Control and navigation framework for quadrotor helicopters." *Journal of intelligent & robotic systems* 70 (2013): 1-12.
- [16] Lewis, David D., Yiming Yang, Tony Russell-Rose, and Fan Li. "Rcv1: A new benchmark collection for text categorization research." *Journal of machine learning research* 5, no. Apr (2004): 361-397.
- [17] Nise, Norman S. *Control systems engineering*. John Wiley & Sons, 2020.
- [18] Kumar, E. Vinodh, and Jovitha Jerome. "Robust LQR controller design for stabilizing and trajectory tracking of inverted pendulum." *Procedia Engineering* 64 (2013): 169-178.
- [19] Cheraghchi, Fatemeh, Ibrahim Abualhaol, Rafael Falcon, Rami Abielmona, Bijan Raahemi, and Emil Petriu. "Modeling the speed-based vessel schedule recovery problem using evolutionary multi-objective optimization." *Information Sciences* 448 (2018): 53-74.

- [20] Khoygani, Mohamad Reza Rahimi, Reza Ghasemi, and Davoud Sanaei. "Design controller for a class of nonlinear pendulum dynamical system." *IAES International Journal of Artificial Intelligence* 2, no. 4 (2013): 159.
- [21] Cheraghchi, Fatemeh, Ibrahim Abualhaol, Rafael Falcon, Rami Abielmona, Bijan Raahemi, and Emil Petriu. "Modeling the speed-based vessel schedule recovery problem using evolutionary multiobjective optimization." *Information Sciences* 448 (2018): 53-74.